

1 **MALDI-TOF MS-Based Lipidomic Profile of Honey**
2 **and Bee Pollen**

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11 **Abstract**

12 The increasing demand for bee-derived products such as honey and bee pollen has led to a rise in
13 adulteration and mislabelling, making it essential to develop reliable tools for authentication. Lipids,
14 which are found in both matrices, are potential biomarkers for tracing their origin, and may be used for
15 detecting fraud. In this work, a solid-liquid extraction using hexane:isopropanol (10:1, v/v) followed by
16 matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization time-of-flight mass spectrometry (MALDI-TOF MS)
17 detection was optimized. The method was applied for tentative lipid screening of 15 honeys and 13 bee
18 pollens showing a total number of lipids above 700, including fatty acyls, glycerolipids,
19 glycerophospholipids, sphingolipids and sterol lipids. For the first time, a principal component analysis,
20 was carried out for botanical and geographical origin, classifying most of the samples correctly.
21 Additionally, the method was categorized as green (environmentally friendly) and blue (practical).

22

23 **Keywords:** MALDI-TOF MS; lipid profiling; lipidomics; food chemistry; bee product; food
24 authentication; metrics; green analytical chemistry; biomarker; principal component analysis; PCA.

25 **1. Introduction**

26 In recent years, bee-derived products, such as honey and bee pollen, have attracted increasing
27 attention due to their rich composition in bioactive compounds with recognized health benefits.^{1,2}
28 Their chemical composition is shaped by multiple factors, with botanical and geographical origins
29 being the most influential.³⁻⁵ Nonetheless, environmental conditions and beekeeping practices
30 also add to the variability observed in these products. Because of this strong correlation between
31 composition and origin, chemical profiling of these products has long served as a reliable means
32 to assess authenticity, preventing false origin labelling, that is, fraud.⁶ Recently, a new regulation
33 related to these products has been published, that is the Royal Decree 68/2025, dated February
34 4th, which amends Royal Decree 1049/2003 of August 1st, approving the quality standard for
35 honey. Determining the floral source of both bee pollen and honey necessitates microscopic
36 examination of pollen grains, a technique known as melissopalynology,⁷ a method which
37 demands highly trained specialists. It can also be complemented by both sensory evaluation and
38 physico-chemical characterization, but this often lacks specificity, and cannot be reliably
39 generalized across all bee pollen and honey types.⁸ As a result, there has been growing interest in
40 developing faster yet dependable strategies for distinguishing honeys according to their floral
41 origin. These alternative methodologies typically involve the assessment of multiple chemical
42 parameters combined with multivariate statistical tools, such as elemental analyser/liquid
43 chromatography-isotope ratio mass spectrometry, high-performance anion exchange
44 chromatography with pulsed amperometric detection, and proton nuclear magnetic resonance
45 spectroscopy.⁹ These can be applied in order to detect biomarkers. A biomarker is a molecule
46 whose presence, composition, or abundance reflects authenticity-related attributes of a biological
47 system such as species, geographical origin, processing history, or freshness, since these
48 characteristics are genetically determined and specifically expressed through the organism's
49 metabolism.¹⁰ So, fully determining the composition is the key to detecting food fraud. In this
50 context, bee pollen is a complex matrix containing essential amino acids, antioxidants, vitamins,

51 and lipids.¹ The latter, in particular, are crucial as energy reserves and structural components,
52 needed for pollen grain viability and germination. Depending on its botanical source, lipid content
53 in bee pollen can vary significantly, ranging from 1% to 20% of its dry weight.¹¹ Honey, while
54 mainly composed of carbohydrates (typically between 60–85%) and water (12–23%), also
55 contains minor compounds such as organic acids, minerals, vitamins, enzymes, proteins, amino
56 acids, and lipids.¹² This last fraction has been found only in trace amounts—around 0.04%—and
57 includes glycerides, sterols, phospholipids, and fatty acids such as palmitic, oleic, lauric, myristic,
58 stearic, and linoleic acids.¹¹ Notably, the natural presence of bee pollen grains in honey may lead
59 to the incidental incorporation of additional compounds typical of the bee pollen matrix. Other
60 constituents of honey and bee pollen, such as amino acids¹³ and glucosinolates,¹⁴ have already
61 been proposed as effective biomarkers for determining botanical and/or geographical origin,
62 highlighting the value of these matrices for product authentication. In this context, lipids, which
63 are also present in both of these bee matrices, emerge as promising candidates for biomarkers due
64 to their structural diversity and sensitivity to environmental and botanical factors.

65 Lipidomics are gaining prominence in the areas of food authentication and the detection of
66 adulteration.¹⁵ Various analytical techniques have been employed to profile lipid compositions in
67 different food matrices. For instance, ultra-high-performance liquid chromatography (UHPLC)
68 coupled with different mass spectrometry detectors, has been applied to uncover fraudulent
69 practices in green tea,¹⁵ or to differentiate toxic from non-toxic mushroom species through the
70 identification of lipid markers.¹⁶ Other matrices analysed with this technique are fish fillets¹⁷ or
71 coffee beans.¹⁸ However, limited information about lipids in bee products is available. Gas
72 chromatography coupled with flame ionization detection (GC-FID) has been used to provide a
73 qualitative analysis of fatty acids in honey, bee pollen, bee bread, and propolis.¹⁹ Matrix-assisted
74 laser desorption/ionization time-of-flight mass spectrometry (MALDI-TOF MS) has also been
75 used for lipid fingerprinting and microbiome characterization.²⁰ It exhibits good characteristics
76 for a fast and sensitive generation of tentative molecular profiles with minimal sample prep

77 optimization, which is aligned with green analytical chemistry (GAC) principles.²¹ This feature
78 is particularly advantageous for preliminary studies, as it provides a broad overview of the sample
79 composition and facilitates the identification of a larger number of potential biomarkers. Once the
80 initial pool of compounds is narrowed down, targeted and quantitative techniques could be
81 applied for more focused validation. This technique has been already applied to detect lipids in a
82 variety of food matrices such as milk,²² oil,²³ rice,²⁴ and lentils,²⁵ being 2,5-dihydroxybenzoic acid
83 (DHB) and chloroform the MALDI matrix and extraction solvent most frequently reported,
84 respectively (see Supporting Information **Table 1S**). In the aforementioned studies, these analytes
85 belonged to the five major lipid families included in the Lipid Metabolites and Pathways Strategy
86 database (LIPID MAPS®)²⁶: fatty acyls, glycerophospholipids, sphingolipids, and sterol lipids.

87 In this work, we propose an optimized sample preparation protocol followed by MALDI-TOF
88 MS analysis for the tentative profiling of lipids in honey and bee pollen. The advantages of using
89 lipids as biomarkers stem from the simplicity and efficiency of the workflow. Sample preparation
90 is minimal, MALDI-TOF MS supports rapid, high-throughput analysis, and the method can
91 deliver an overview of the sample's composition. This approach enables both the generation of a
92 global fingerprint and, when necessary, the targeted monitoring of specific lipids of interest. This
93 approach aims to support the discrimination of both botanical and geographical origins based on
94 the full lipid profile in the sample. To date, only one study²⁷ has reported lipid profiling in bee
95 pollen and none in honey, underscoring the novelty and relevance of the present research.
96 Understanding the lipid profile of bee-derived products not only contributes to their authentication
97 but also provides insights into their nutritional quality and potential health benefits.

98

99 **2. Materials and Methods**

100 *2.1. Reagents and Instrumentation*

101 All solvents (tetrahydrofuran, hexane, isopropanol, methanol, chloroform, heptane, cyclohexane,
102 and dichloromethane) were of chromatographic grade and were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich
103 (Madrid, Spain), Carlo Erba Reagents, and Panreac Química (Barcelona, Spain). The calibrant
104 for MALDI-TOF, polyethylene glycol (PEG 1000, 10 mg/mL), was purchased from Sigma-
105 Aldrich (Steinheim, Germany). MALDI matrices such as 3',5'-dimethoxy-4-
106 hydroxyacetophenone (DHAP), dithranol (DIT), trans-2-[3-(4-tert-butylphenyl)-2-methyl-2-
107 propenylidene]malononitrile (DCTB), 2,5-dihydroxybenzoic acid (DHB), cinnamic chloride
108 (CC), 4-hydroxy-3-methoxycinnamaldehyde (HMCA) and 1-amino-2-naphthol-4-sulfonic acid
109 (AANS), and ionizing agents (silver and sodium trifluoroacetate, AgTFA and NaTFA) were
110 obtained from Sigma-Aldrich (Steinheim, Germany).

111 Laboratory equipment included an EA-240 analytical balance (Mettler Toledo, Darmstadt,
112 Germany), ThermoFisher micropipettes (Waltham, MA, USA), and Eppendorf tubes (Labbox SL,
113 Barcelona, Spain). Sample mixing and processing were performed using a Heidolph vortex
114 mechanical mixer (Schwabach, Germany), a Vibromatic mechanical shaker and an ultrasound
115 bath both supplied by J.P. Selecta S.A. (Barcelona, Spain). Centrifugation was conducted using
116 an Eppendorf refrigerated benchtop centrifuge (Hamburg, Germany).

117

118 *2.2. Samples*

119 A total of 28 samples were analysed (see **Table 1**), including 15 honey and 13 bee pollen samples.
120 The honey samples were from different botanical origins determined through
121 melissopalynological analysis such as multifloral, chestnut (*Castanea sativa*), sainfoin
122 (*Onobrychis viciifolia*), rapeseed (*Brassica napus*), lavender (*Lavandula spp.*), clover (*Trifolium*
123 *spp.*), and heather (*Erica spp.*) honeys. Similarly, the bee pollen samples consisted of 10

124 multifloral and 3 chestnut bee pollen specimens. All samples were collected from different
125 geographic regions across Spain. Honey samples were stored at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ until analysis to preserve
126 their lipid composition. Bee pollen samples were dried in an oven at $45\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 24 hours, ground
127 individually using a mill, pooled to ensure optimal sample homogeneity and subsequently stored
128 in a dry-seal vacuum desiccator at room temperature until analysis.²⁸ Three replicates (sub-
129 samples) of each sample, which were analysed in triplicate, were examined to determine the lipid
130 content.

131 *2.3. Sample Treatment*

132 The sample preparation protocols to extract lipids from honey and bee pollen were designed to be
133 simple, reproducible, and fast, and are largely comparable. Both methods are illustrated in **Figure**
134 **1**.

135 *2.3.1. Honey Samples*

136 Briefly, 750 mg of homogenized honey was weighed into a 10 mL centrifuge tube. A volume of
137 2 mL of a mixture of hexane:isopropanol (10:1 v/v) was then added. The mixture was shaken
138 using a Vibromatic shaker for 5 minutes and the samples were centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 3
139 minutes at room temperature, allowing the solid phase to settle at the bottom of the tube. The
140 resulting supernatant was decanted and collected for subsequent MALDI-TOF MS analysis.

141 *2.3.2. Bee Pollen Samples*

142 Briefly, 99 mg of homogenized bee pollen was weighed in a 10 mL centrifuge tube, followed by
143 addition of 2 mL of a hexane:isopropanol (10:1 v/v). The mixture was agitated for 48 seconds in
144 a vortex device and subsequently centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 3 minutes at room temperature.
145 The supernatant was then decanted and used for MALDI-TOF MS lipid profiling.

146

147 2.4. MALDI-TOF Conditions

148 Lipid profiling was performed using MALDI-TOF MS in positive reflector mode. The instrument
149 (Autoflex® maX, Bruker Daltonics, Bremen, Germany) was equipped with a laser operating at a
150 wavelength of 335 nm, a frequency of 1000 Hz and using a 5 GS/s digitizer. The dynamic range
151 was set from m/z 200 to 2200, and a suppression gate up to m/z 350 was applied to prevent detector
152 saturation by low-mass ions, especially from the MALDI matrix. The laser power was set to 50%
153 for both honey and bee pollen samples. PEG 1000 in tetrahydrofuran (10 mg mL^{-1}) was used as a
154 calibrant with DCTB as the MALDI matrix (PEG 1000:DCTB, 4:10, v/v), and the calibration
155 error was of 0.3 Da. The MALDI matrix used for the analyses was DHAP in dichloromethane (15
156 mg mL^{-1}), and the ionizing agent was an AgTFA solution in tetrahydrofuran (10 mg mL^{-1}). For
157 honey samples, the sample-to-matrix-to-ionizing agent ratio was 1:1:0.25 (v/v/v), whereas for bee
158 pollen the ratio was 1:1:0.5 (v/v/v). To improve reproducibility and ensure more homogeneous
159 crystallization, the sample, MALDI matrix, and ionizing agent were mixed in an Eppendorf tube
160 immediately prior to deposition of $0.5 \mu\text{L}$ of the mixture onto the MALDI plate. Spectra
161 acquisition and processing were performed under standardized conditions. Lipids were tentatively
162 identified by comparing experimental m/z values to entries in the LIPID MAPS® database²⁹ with
163 a mass accuracy threshold of less than ± 0.05 Da. Lipid signals were assigned based on the
164 database entry with the lowest mass error relative to the experimental m/z value. To improve
165 identification reliability and minimize false positives arising from MALDI matrix-related signals,
166 spectra were also acquired from the MALDI matrix, prepared with the same matrix-to-ionizing
167 agent ratio used in the sample mixtures. This allowed for the subtraction of MALDI matrix-
168 derived peaks from the lipid profiles of each sample. MALDI matrix-only controls were recorded
169 freshly on each analytical day to account for possible day-to-day variability.

170

171 *2.5. Statistical Analysis*

172 Design of experiments (DoE) was conducted using MODDE 13.1 (Sartorius Stedim Data
173 Analytics AB). Multivariate statistical analyses were performed to evaluate the discriminative
174 power of the lipid profiles obtained from honey and bee pollen samples. Principal component
175 analysis (PCA) was carried out using the PROC CANDISC procedure in SAS software, version
176 9.4 (SAS Institute Inc., Cary, NC, USA), to assess the separation between groups based on
177 botanical and geographical origin.

178

179 **3. Results and Discussion**

180 *3.1. Preliminary Tests*

181 To establish optimal extraction conditions for lipid profiling of honey and bee pollen by MALDI-
182 TOF MS, preliminary experiments were conducted comparing several solvents and solvent
183 mixtures in different proportions. These are very different matrices both in terms of structure and
184 composition, so the sample treatment might differ and they cannot be considered as equivalent,
185 although that would be optimal. Plus, both are very complex and can lead to interferences, which
186 would be specially inconvenient for untargeted analyses, and so, an initial extraction of the
187 compounds of interest is crucial. Both solid-liquid and liquid-liquid extraction approaches were
188 evaluated to identify conditions yielding the highest number of mass spectral signals attributable
189 to lipids, as confirmed by database matching in LIPID MAPS®.²⁹ Solvents most used in the
190 literature included chloroform,³⁰ methanol³¹ or mixtures of the both of them,³² as well as some
191 other organic solvents such as hexane²³ or dichloromethane.³³ These and some others were tested
192 as can be seen in **Table 2**. Initial tests according to available sample amount used 20-minute
193 ultrasonic extraction with a solvent volume of 2 mL and sample amounts of 500 mg for honey
194 and 10 mg for bee pollen. It must be mentioned that in every case, bee pollen had to be grinded
195 in order to be able to access the lipids in the inside of the grains, as bee pollen composition varies

196 from the outer layers to the inner ones.³⁴ Furthermore, there can be slight differences between
197 different bee pollen grains in the same lot, so this can provide more representative results overall.
198 After the extraction, centrifugation was needed in order to separate the solid residue of the
199 samples and facilitate decantation. This was set for 3 minutes at 10,000 rpm as it provided
200 adequate separation. Liquid-liquid extractions were performed only for honey and consisted in
201 dissolving the sample in 2 mL of water before adding the organic solvent. The results indicated
202 that these extractions were less efficient than solid-liquid ones. Detection in these experiments
203 was performed in positive mode as this allowed for the detection of a broader range of lipid
204 families and therefore has been more usually employed in similar studies.^{23,35,36} No ionizing agent
205 was used, and DCTB was selected as the MALDI matrix, in a 1:1 ratio with the sample. Among
206 the tested solvents, the mixture hexane:isopropanol (10:1, v/v) provided the most numerous lipid-
207 related signals with minimal interference from MALDI matrix peaks. It must also be mentioned
208 that higher proportions of isopropanol, as well as other alcohols, led to spreading of the extractant
209 across the MALDI target wells, resulting in cross-contamination between samples. It is also worth
210 noting that the mass range used in the literature typically extends from m/z 200 to 2000,^{22,37} with
211 only a few studies extending the upper limit to m/z 4000 or 5000.^{38,39} In this work, a range from
212 m/z 350 to 2200 was selected to maximize lipid detection while remaining within a range
213 comparable to most published articles.

214 Moreover, several MALDI matrices, namely DIT, DCTB, DHB, CC, DHAP, and AANS, were
215 evaluated to identify the optimal MALDI matrix for selective detection of lipid signals, as they
216 are representative compounds belonging to the families most used for this purpose (benzoic acid
217 derivatives, cinnamic acid derivatives, heterocycles and others).⁴⁰ Some of them were discarded
218 in terms of their performance. Firstly, AANS was excluded due to spontaneous and highly
219 irregular precipitation, in some stances even before deposition, varying concentration of the
220 MALDI matrix solution. Other options such as DIT and CC, produced few background signals,
221 which is desirable; however, they yielded negligible signals from the sample, often limited to

222 MALDI matrix-derived peaks or background noise. Adversely, DCTB generated a high number
223 of signals in the m/z 400-1000 range, interfering with sample signal detection and interpretation.
224 DHB which has been more widely reported (see Supporting Information **Table 1S**), gave good
225 results in positive mode, but both this MALDI matrix and HMCA showed fewer lipid signals in
226 the samples compared to DHAP (see Supporting Information Figure 1S). Therefore, the selected
227 MALDI matrix was the latter, as it provided the best results, crystallizing homogeneously and
228 producing fewer signals at higher m/z values. Most lipid-related signals with DHAP were
229 observed below m/z 400, facilitating clear lipid profiling with minimal MALDI matrix
230 overlapping over this value. The signals below were therefore not considered in the analysis.

231 In the reviewed literature, ionizing agents are not usually applied, but some works opted for
232 introducing sodium (NaTFA or NaCl)⁴¹⁻⁴³ cations for a better performance and silver is a well-
233 known cation as well.⁴⁴ For its evaluation, two ionizing agents (AgTFA and NaTFA) were tested,
234 dissolved in methanol and tetrahydrofuran. NaTFA produced very few sample-related signals in
235 both solvents, suggesting poor interaction or ionization efficiency under the tested conditions. In
236 contrast, AgTFA performed well in terms of improving the intensity of the signals, and therefore,
237 the number of detected peaks. AgTFA in tetrahydrofuran was selected as it facilitated more
238 uniform spot deposition on the MALDI target plate, given that it has higher surface tension and
239 extends less around the plate.

240 Furthermore, in order to improve reproducibility, the sample, the MALDI matrix, and the ionizing
241 agent were mixed thoroughly in a 0.5 mL Eppendorf tube prior to deposition of 0.5 μ L on the
242 target plate, rather than sequentially depositing each component directly into the well. Mixing
243 was performed using the micropipette tip inside the tube, ensuring homogeneous suspension and
244 preventing variability caused by uneven crystallization and poor spreading, especially of the
245 ionizing agent. This modification significantly enhanced spectral reproducibility across replicate
246 analyses.

247

248 3.2. Optimization of the Detection

249 Negative ion mode was initially tested as part of the analytical procedure; however, no signals
250 were detected and as a result, no further optimization was pursued in this mode, and the
251 corresponding data are not shown in this work. Following this, once the MALDI matrix (DHAP),
252 ionizing agent (AgTFA) and extractant solvent (hexane, isopropanol, 10:1, v/v) were set, the
253 detection parameters including laser power and sample:matrix:ionizing agent ratios were
254 optimized (see **Table 3**). The evaluation was based on the total number of signals assigned to
255 lipid species after subtracting those detected in the MALDI matrix-only controls, and
256 reproducibility was assessed by consecutive measurements.

257 In terms of laser power, the literature for the analysis of lipids in food has a considerably ample
258 range, from 10%³⁰ to 95%⁴⁵, as it depends on both the MALDI matrix and the sample. In our case,
259 this parameter was tested in the range of 30% to 80%. Spectra acquired at 30%, showed very low
260 signal intensity and therefore a significantly lower number of signals (see **Figure 2** and best
261 conditions in Supporting Information **Table 2S** and **Figure 2S** for honey, and Supporting
262 Information **Figure 3S** for bee pollen), so lower percentages of laser power were not applied. At
263 the maximum power, 80%, sample suffered thermal degradation, compromising reproducibility;
264 thus, results at that setting were not included in **Table 3**, and no higher power was tested. Although
265 intensities at 50% and 60% laser power were comparable, 50% yielded a higher number of
266 identifiable lipid peaks. Notably, some of the additional peaks observed at 60% appeared at higher
267 m/z values but could not be confidently assigned to any lipid species in the LIPID MAPS®
268 database²⁹ within the accepted mass error threshold, and therefore, these were excluded from
269 analysis. Both the previous and the subtraction of MALDI matrix peaks that could be more intense
270 due to the laser power being higher might be the causes of a slightly higher number of signals at
271 50% laser power.

272 The ratio between sample, MALDI matrix, and ionizing agent also affected the number of lipids
273 detected. Excessive proportion of AgTFA led to a dominance of MALDI matrix-derived peaks
274 and a decrease in lipid-identifiable signals, or in some cases, the appearance of non-attributable
275 peaks. After testing ratios from 1:1:0.25 to 1:1:1, the optimal composition was determined to be
276 1:1:0.25 for honey samples and 1:1:0.5 for bee pollen samples (see **Table 3**).

277

278 *3.3. Optimization of the Sample Treatment Using Design of Experiments*

279 Next step was focused on optimizing sample preparation parameters, specifically sample amount
280 and extraction time. For this, a quadratic model using central composite face-centered (CCF)
281 design was implemented, aiming to maximize the response variable, which was defined as the
282 number of lipid signals detected after database matching with LIPID MAPS[®],²⁹ and also after
283 subtraction of MALDI matrix-related peaks, as described previously. The factor levels were
284 coded as high (+1), central point (0), low (-1) levels. For honey, the sample weight factor varied
285 between 250 and 750 mg, while for bee pollen it ranged from 10 mg to 100 mg. These values
286 agreed with previous published articles, which are mostly lower than 1 g (see Supporting
287 Information **Table 1S**), and are also related to the amounts of sample availability. Extraction time
288 was evaluated for each of three extraction methods; ultrasonic bath and Vibromatic shaker times
289 were tested from 5 to 15 minutes, whereas vortex went between 30 and 90 seconds. The software
290 generated a total of 11 experimental runs for each extraction device, resulting in 33 trials per
291 sample type (honey and bee pollen, respectively).

292 For honey samples, after fitting individual models for each extraction technique, the Vibromatic
293 shaker yielded the highest number of lipid-associated signals under optimal conditions, with a
294 total of 52 lipids detected. Therefore, this method was selected for further discussion. The best
295 model fitting was obtained by transforming the response using the negative logarithmic function,
296 $\text{NegLog}(-10 \times \log(100 - Y))$, where Y represents the number of lipid signals. Significant factors

297 in the model included sample amount, extraction time, and two of their interaction terms: amount
298 with itself and with time. The model showed good statistical parameters, such as a R^2 of 0.976,
299 Q^2 of 0.849 (classified as good model by MODDE), model validity of 0.936, reproducibility of
300 0.905, and a relative standard deviation (RSD) of 0.010. The response contour plot (see **Figure**
301 **3A**) indicated that optimal conditions were achieved using 750 mg of honey and 5 min of agitation
302 using the Vibromatic shaker.

303 For bee pollen samples, after fitting and optimizing the models for each extraction device, the
304 vortex mixer provided the highest number of lipid-associated signals under optimal conditions,
305 this being 57 signals. Consequently, this method was selected for discussion in this case. The best
306 model performance was achieved by transforming the response using the logarithmic function
307 $\text{Log}(10 \times \log(Y))$, where, again, Y corresponds to the number of lipid signals. Significant factors
308 included extraction time, and the same interaction terms as before. For this MALDI matrix, R^2
309 was of 0.979, Q^2 of 0.878 (good model), model validity of 0.970, reproducibility of 0.857, and
310 RSD of 0.034. The contour plot of the response surface (see **Figure 3B**) shows the optimal
311 conditions which were 99 mg of bee pollen and 48 seconds of vortex mixing. It must be mentioned
312 that although problematic experimental runs in terms of statistical results were repeated, three
313 data points still had to be excluded from the dataset to ensure proper model fitting and predictive
314 reliability for this MALDI matrix.

315

316 *3.4. Application of the Method*

317 The optimized method was applied to a total of 15 honey and 13 bee pollen samples of diverse
318 botanical and geographical origins (see **Table 1**). For each sample, signals from spectra were sent
319 to LIPID MAPS®,²⁹ and the MALDI matrix signals were removed. Then, using the list generated
320 by the database, a construction of a global lipid profile table was carried out for each kind of
321 sample. In instances where a single plausible option remained, that lipid was reported. When

322 multiple candidate identifications were obtained, we considered not only the closest mass match
323 but also the chemical plausibility of the adduct. For example, Ag⁺ adducts were retained given
324 their direct connection to the ionizing agent employed. Confidence in these assignments was
325 further strengthened when both ¹⁰⁷Ag and ¹⁰⁹Ag adducts were observed for the same lipid species.
326 The compiled data was then employed to carry out a PCA for honey and bee pollen in terms of
327 botanical and geographical origin.

328 Complete tables linking each code to its corresponding lipid are provided in the Supporting
329 Information **Tables 3S** and **4S**. Lipid species are referred to using the terms HL (honey lipid) and
330 PL (bee pollen lipid), respectively, followed by the numerical code assigned during statistical
331 analysis. It should be noted that the same lipid may have different codes in honey and bee pollen
332 datasets, depending on their order within each sample.

333 *3.4.1. Honey*

334 A total of 375 distinct lipid species were detected across the 15 honey samples analysed (H1 to
335 H15), and the PCA reduced the variable set to 12 principal components that together explained
336 94% of the variance. Among the most relevant lipids contributing to this PCA were ST 30:6;O7,
337 FA 28:7, FAHFA 33:3;O, LPE 14:1, LPE 17:2, LPG 18:3, LPG O-16:0, MIPC 44:0;O2, PG O-
338 38:3, PI 43:6, PS O-41:1, ST 24:0;O4 and ST 26:0;O5. Using these components, the analysis
339 allowed for classification of all honey samples according to their botanical origin (see Supporting
340 Information **Table 5S**). The average values of the first two principal components are represented
341 in **Figure 4A**, where clear separation between botanical groups is observed. Regarding
342 geographical origin, differentiation was also seen among the three identified regions, as illustrated
343 in **Figure 4B**. Samples labelled as “Spain” correspond to those not falling within the other two
344 specific regions. Again, 100% classification accuracy was achieved (see Supporting Information
345 **Table 6S**), confirming the method’s strong potential to differentiate honeys based on both
346 botanical and geographical origin through their lipidomic profiles.

347 To better visualize the lipid distribution, **Figure 5A** presents the relative proportion of each major
348 lipid class in a color-coded graph. This shows that all lipid families were detected across the honey
349 samples except in H5, where no sphingolipids were observed. Overall, glycerophospholipids was
350 the most abundant family (37%), followed by sterol lipids (24%) and then sphingolipids (19%),
351 fatty acyls (11%) and glycerolipids (9%). However, it is important to note that this observation is
352 based on the variety of lipid species detected, as no quantitative analysis was performed. It is also
353 worth noting that certain lipids were particularly recurrent across the honey samples. For instance,
354 lipids FA 36:0 and WE 36:0 were found in all 15 samples. Lipids PC 41:0 and PE 44:0 appeared
355 in 13 out of 15, both missing from H1. Additionally, a group of lipids (ACer 50:1;O2, DG 44:2,
356 MIPC 36:0;O2, PC 44:1, PC O-42:1, and ST 21:2;O3;S) were consistently absent in the same
357 three samples (H5, H6, and H7).

358 *3.4.2. Bee pollen*

359 In this case, a total of 337 lipid species were identified across the 13 bee pollen samples (P1 to
360 P13). The PCA reduced the dataset to 10 principal components and these together accounted for
361 92% of the variance. The most relevant lipids contributing to this model were CE 22:4, FA 42:0;O,
362 LPE 18:3, PA 40:0, PA O-40:2, PG 33:0, PI O-38:1, ST 28:0;O5. Based on this PCA, 11 out of
363 the 13 samples were classified according to their botanical origin (see **Table 7S**, Supporting
364 Information). **Figure 4C** illustrates the average values for each group, showing clear
365 differentiation among them. For geographical origin, the samples exhibited a clear separation
366 between the four regions considered. This is shown in **Figure 4D**, where 100% classification
367 accuracy was achieved (see **Table 8S**, Supporting Information). Unlike with honey, there were
368 more multifloral samples available, and so, an additional analysis was carried out to assess
369 whether a geographical differentiation could be achieved within the same botanical origin. As
370 shown in **Table 9S** (Supporting Information), the classification by geographical origin was
371 successful. **Figure 4E** displays the average PCA values, illustrating a good separation between
372 geographical origins within this botanical group.

373 **Figure 5B** illustrates the distribution of lipid classes per bee pollen sample in the same way it was
374 considered for honey, showing that all lipid families were detected across the samples. Overall,
375 glycerophospholipids was the most abundant family (44%), followed by sterol lipids (26%), and
376 then glycerolipids (11%), fatty acyls (10%) and sphingolipids (9%) in proportions quite similar
377 to honey as well. Lipids PC 42:3, PC 42:4, PC 44:3, PS O-42:0, ST 19:2;O3, and TG 43:0 were
378 present in all 13 samples. Lipids Cer 44:0;O4 and HexCer 38:0;O2 appeared in 12 of them,
379 missing only in sample P5, while DG 44:2 was detected in 11 samples, absent in P2 and P9.

380

381 *3.4.3. Merits of the proposed method*

382 The present study is highly novel, as up-to-date only one publication²⁷ reported the use of
383 MALDI-TOF MS to analyse the lipid profile in bee pollen samples. Moreover, lipids in honey
384 have never been determined by this technique and only a few works have taken this family of
385 analytes into account.^{6,46,47} Some early works indicated probable presence of TGs, STs, GPs⁴⁷ or
386 cholesterol esters (CEs)⁴⁶ in honey samples. Similarly, we have found lipid signals related to all
387 of the previously mentioned families (see Supporting Information **Table 3S**). The lipidic profiles
388 reported in our article show promising results as they indicate that these bioactive compounds
389 might be relevant to distinguishing between samples from different botanical and geographical
390 origins. In order to obtain these tentative lipidomes, sample preparation and detection conditions
391 were exhaustively optimized, including a design of experiments. With our work, we contribute
392 additional data to the scientific literature and set the foundations for further research in
393 constituents in food matrices with potential for biomarker applications. However, further research
394 is needed to expand the analysis to a broader range of samples from different botanical families
395 and geographical regions.

396

397 4. Green & Blue Assessment

398 In the field of analytical chemistry, recent efforts have focused on developing methodologies that
399 align with the principles of white analytical chemistry (WAC).⁴⁸ This multidimensional approach
400 seeks not only analytical efficiency (red, R), but also environmental sustainability (green, G) and
401 practical applicability (blue, B).⁴⁹ Since the early 2020s, a wide variety of tools, metrics, and
402 templates have been introduced in this context, aimed not only at assessing the RGB dimensions,
403 but also at evaluating the innovativeness of analytical methods,⁵⁰ and even at visually presenting
404 their main features and results.⁵¹ For the red dimension, the red analytical performance index
405 (RAPI) was proposed to evaluate analytical performance, including key validation parameters.⁵²
406 However, as the proposed MALDI-TOF method was not designed or optimized for quantitative
407 analysis, but rather for exploratory lipid profiling and comparative purposes, this dimension was
408 not considered. As in previous studies,²⁸ both the green and blue dimensions were thoroughly
409 assessed using the analytical GREENness calculator (AGREE),⁵³ the modified green analytical
410 procedure index (MoGAPI),⁵⁴ and the blue applicability grade index (BAGI),⁵⁵ respectively (see
411 Supporting Information, **Figure 4S**). All three tools are freely available with user-friendly
412 software and implementation guidelines.

413 AGREE offers a comprehensive sustainability assessment based on the twelve principles of green
414 analytical chemistry,⁵⁶ transformed into a 0-1 scoring scale. The final score reflects the combined
415 contribution of all principles, and results are visualized as a circular pictogram using a red-yellow-
416 green colour gradient. A method is generally considered “green” when the score exceeds 0.6.
417 MoGAPI provides a more detailed evaluation of method greenness by incorporating a broader
418 range of parameters with stricter and more specific criteria. Results are displayed in a pentagonal
419 chart using the same colour-based system.

420 As displayed in **Figure 4SA** and **Figure 4SB**, the AGREE scores differed slightly between honey
421 and bee pollen according to their sample preparation workflows (see **Figure 1**). Offline

422 measurements (principle 3), and the high energy consumption of MALDI-TOF MS (principle 9)
423 were negatively weighted by the AGREE metric (see **Figure 4SA**). In contrast, the minimal
424 sample size (principle 2), a fast sample preparation process involving just a few steps (extraction
425 and centrifugation, principle 4) without derivatization (principle 6), the possibility of
426 simultaneous detection of a high number of analytes and samples per hour (principle 8), and the
427 operator safety (principle 12) were highlighted in green. It is important to note that, although the
428 energy consumption of the instrument is high compared to others, the use of MALDI-TOF MS is
429 the best option for tentative lipidic profiling. The final AGREE scores were 0.66 for honey and
430 0.68 for bee pollen, both above the optimal threshold (0.6), indicating that the proposed analytical
431 methods were environmentally friendly. Regarding MoGAPI (see **Figure 4SC**), the score
432 obtained was 70 out of 100, which corresponded to a moderate environmental impact. The results
433 obtained agreed with the previous tool. Some benefits highlighted in green included easy and fast
434 sample preparation, low sample and solvent amounts. By contrast, the main drawbacks stem from
435 the use of non-green organic solvents (isopropanol, hexane, and dichloromethane), the off-line
436 collection and the energy consumption.

437 The applicability of an analytical method was evaluated by the blue applicability grade index
438 (BAGI).⁵⁵ This metric based on ten attributes generates a pictogram that reflects the practicality.
439 A sequential blue colour scale ranging from dark blue (high compliance) to white (no
440 compliance), is employed to visually represent the final score. According to BAGI guidelines, a
441 final score exceeding 60.0 points is recommended for a method to be considered practical. The
442 proposed method achieved a score of 75. One of the penalties was the use of MALDI-TOF
443 instrumentation, which is not widely available in all laboratories. Similarly, partial automation of
444 the procedure also lowered the score, as some steps were performed manually. However, the use
445 of MALDI-TOF provided fast and accurate analysis for a high number of samples and the
446 simplicity and low cost of the sample preparation and extraction steps, as well as the small sample
447 amount required, contributed positively to the final score. For the first time, three metrics were

448 applied to a MALDI-TOF MS lipidomic study for apicultural products, and they categorized the
449 method as green (environmentally friendly) and blue (practical).

450

451 **Abbreviations Used**

452 **AANS**, 1-amino-2-naphthol-4-sulfonic acid; **AGREE**, analytical GREENness calculator;
453 **AgTFA**, silver trifluoroacetate; **BAGI**, blue applicability grade index; **CC**, cinnamic chloride;
454 **CCF**, central composite face-centered; **CE**, cholesterol ester; **DCTB**, trans-2-[3-(4-tert-
455 Butylphenyl)-2-methyl-2-propenylidene]malononitrile; **DHAP**, 3',5'-dimethoxy-4-
456 hydroxyacetophenone; **DHB**, 2,5-dihydroxybenzoic acid; **DIT**, dithranol; **DoE**, design of
457 experiments; **GAC**, green analytical chemistry; **GC-FID**, gas chromatography coupled with
458 flame ionization detection; **H**, honey; **HL**, honey lipid; **HMCA**, 4-hydroxy-3-
459 methoxycinnamaldehyde; **HX**, hexane; **IPA**, isopropanol; **LIPID MAPS®**, lipid metabolites and
460 pathways strategy; **LMSD**, LIPID MAPS® structure database; **MoGAPI**, modified green
461 analytical procedure index; **NaTFA**, sodium trifluoroacetate; **P**, bee pollen; **PCA**, principal
462 component analysis; **PEG**, polyethylene glycol; **PL**, bee pollen lipid; **RAPI**, red analytical
463 performance index; **RSD**, relative standard deviation; **THF**, tetrahydrofuran; **UHPLC**, ultra-
464 high-performance liquid chromatography; **WAC**, white analytical chemistry.

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469

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473

474 **Conflict of Interest Statement**

475 The authors of this manuscript declare no conflict of interest.

476

477 **Data Availability**

478 The datasets generated during the current study are included in this published article, or they are
479 available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

480

481 **Supporting Information**

482 Additional experimental details including chromatograms, PCA data tables, lipid codes and green
483 and blue metrics used in this work and cited as Table XS and Figure XS throughout the text
484 (DOC).

485

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Figure Captions

Figure 1. Sample preparation workflows for honey and bee pollen.

Figure 2. Comparative mass spectra of honey samples acquired at 30%, 50%, 60%, and 80% laser intensity in MALDI-TOF MS.

Figure 3. Response contour plots from the design of experiments for sample weight and shaking time during sample preparation for A) honey and B) bee pollen.

Figure 4. Principal component analysis score plots based on mean values for: A) botanical origin in honey, B) geographical origin in honey, C) botanical origin in bee pollen, D) geographical origin in bee pollen, E) geographical origin within the same botanical origin in multifloral bee pollen.

Figure 5. Distribution of lipids across the five main lipid families according to LIPID MAPS®²⁶ in A) honey and B) bee pollen (FA, fatty acyls; ST, sterol lipids; GP, glycerophospholipids; SP, sphingolipids; GL, glycerolipids).

Tables

Table 1. Botanical and Geographical Origins of the Analysed Honey and Bee Pollen Samples.

Honey Samples			Bee Pollen Samples		
Code	Botanical Origin	Geographical Origin	Code	Botanical Origin	Geographical Origin
H1	Multifloral	Salamanca	P1	Multifloral	Spain
H2	Multifloral	Spain	P2	Multifloral	Spain
H3	Chestnut	Galicia	P3	Multifloral	Granada
H4	Chestnut	Ávila	P4	Multifloral	Spain
H5	Multifloral	Ávila	P5	Chestnut	Spain
H6	Multifloral	Cuenca	P6	Multifloral	Galicia
H7	Multifloral	Palencia	P7	Multifloral	Galicia
H8	Sainfoin	Palencia	P8	Multifloral	Spain
H9	Rapeseed	Palencia	P9	Multifloral	Spain
H10	Lavender	Cuenca	P10	Multifloral	Spain
H11	Trifolium	Palencia	P11	Chestnut	Spain
H12	Lavender	Cuenca	P12	Multifloral	Spain
H13	Heather	Palencia	P13	Chestnut	Galicia
H14	Heather	Palencia			
H15	Multifloral	Palencia			

H, honey; P, bee pollen.

Table 2. Number of Lipids Detected for Each Extraction Technique and Solvent Evaluated for Honey and Bee Pollen.

Extraction technique	Solvent(s)	Ratio (v/v)	No. of Lipids (Honey)	No. of Lipids (Bee Pollen)
S-L	MeOH	-	23	28
S-L	CHCl ₃	-	32	24
L-L	CHCl ₃	-	28	-
S-L	IPA	-	19	17
S-L	HX	-	39	33
L-L	HX	-	31	-
S-L	CHCl ₃ :MeOH	1:1	18	21
S-L	CHCl ₃ :MeOH	2:1	27	17
S-L	CHCl ₃ :MeOH	5:1	29	14
S-L	CHCl ₃ :MeOH	10:1	23	14
S-L	HX:IPA	1:1	23	25
S-L	HX:IPA	2:1	31	26
S-L	HX:IPA	5:1	35	30
S-L	HX:IPA	10:1	43	34
S-L	Heptane	-	19	19
L-L	Heptane	-	13	-
S-L	CX	-	29	23
L-L	CX	-	27	-
S-L	DCM	-	27	21
L-L	DCM	-	24	-

CX, cyclohexane; **DCM**, dichloromethane; **HX**, hexane; **IPA**, isopropanol; **L-L**, liquid-liquid extraction; **MeOH**, methanol; **S-L**, solid-liquid extraction.

Table 3. Number of Lipids Detected for Each Condition for MALDI-TOF MS Analysis in Honey and Bee Pollen Samples, Using DHAP in DCM (15 mg mL⁻¹) as the MALDI Matrix and AgTFA in THF (10 mg mL⁻¹) as the Ionizing Agent.

Laser Intensity (%)	Sample:Matrix:Agent (v/v/v)	Lipids (Honey)	Lipids (Bee Pollen)
30	1:1:0.25	13	8
30	1:1:0.5	11	9
30	1:1:1	12	28
50	1:1:0.25	45	36
50	1:1:0.5	40	41
50	1:1:1	42	33
60	1:1:0.25	38	36
60	1:1:0.5	40	32
60	1:1:1	37	29

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SUPPORTING INFORMATION

MALDI-TOF MS-Based Lipidomic Profile of Honey and Bee Pollen

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Table 1S. Overview of Research Articles Using MALDI-TOF for Lipid Analysis in Food Products.

Food Sample	Lipid Family^a	MALDI Matrix	Extraction Solvent	Sample Amount	Ref.
Cod liver oil	GL	DHB	Pentane	50 mg	57
Rice, wheat	GL, GP	9-AA, DHB	MeOH	200 mg	31
Fish	FA	NS	CHCl ₃ :MeOH (2:1)	230 - 300 mg	58
Olive oil,Pâté	GL	DHB	THF	3 g	43
Oat	GL, GP	CHCA	MTBE:MeOH (3:1) or CHCl ₃ :MeOH (2:1)	50 mg	36
Milk	GP	DHB	CHCl ₃ :MeOH (2:1)	2 ml or 2 mg	22
Vegetable oils	FA	F20TPP	MeOH: H ₂ O (4:1)	20 mg	59
Micro and macroalgae	FA, GP, GL	DAN & 9-AA	MeOH:CHCl ₃ (2:1)	200 mg	60
Fish	GP	SA, DHB	NS	NS	61
Bovine and soya milks	GL GP	sDHB	H ₂ O	1 mL	45
Organic milk	FA, GP	DHB, S-DHB, CHCA	MeOH, MTBE	20 µL	35
Green beans	GP	DHB	MTBE:MeOH (1:1)	5 mg	37
Human milk	NS	DHB, SA	NS	1 µL	39
Human milk	FA	DHB	Diisopropylether:1-butanol (6:4)	10 mL	62
Criquet	GL, ST, GL	NS	DCM:MeOH (2:1)	5 g	33
Olive oil	FA	DHB	CHCl ₃	5 mg	41
Animal fat	GL	DHB	CHCl ₃	10 mg	42
Hen egg yolk	GP	DHB, 9-AA	CHCl ₃ :MeOH:H ₂ O (1:1:1)	NS	63
Olive oils	GL	DHB	CHCl ₃	10 mg	64
Algae	GL	sDHB	NS	NS	65
Vegetable oil	GL	DHB & CHCA	No solvent used	NS	66
Edible oils	GL	DHB	HX	1 mg	23
Plant and fungal oils	GL	THAP	CHCl ₃	NS	38
Goat and Sheep Milk	FA, GP, SP	CCICA, CHCA	CHCl ₃ :MeOH (1:2), H ₂ O:CHCl ₃ (1:1)	50 µL	67
Human milk	FA	DHB	CHCl ₃	10 mL	68
Hen egg yolk	GP, SP, GL	Di-FCCA, 9-AA	CHCl ₃ :MeOH:H ₂ O (1:1:1)	NS	69
Bovine meat	GP, FA, GP, GL, ST	CHCA,9-AA	CHCl ₃ :MeOH (2:1)	10 g	70
Rice	GL	DHB	No solvent used	NS	24
Muscle of bulls	GL	DHB, 9-AA	CHCl ₃ :MeOH (2:1)	2 g	32

Algae	GL	DHB	CHCl ₃ :MeOH (2:1)	NS	71
White shrimp	GP	DHB	NS	NS	72
Lentil	GL, GP	CHCA, 9-AA	No solvent used	NS	25
Vegetable oils	GL	DHB	CHCl ₃	1 mg	30
Zebrafsh liver	GP	DAN	No solvent used	NS	73
Peanut Seeds	GL, GP	DHB	No solvent used	NS	74

^aClassification according to LIPID MAPS® Database.²⁶ **9-AA**, 9-aminoacridine; **CCICA**, 4-chloro- α -cyano-cinnamic acid; **CHCA**, α -cyano-4-hydroxycinnamic acid; **CHCl₃**, chloroform; **DAN**, 1,5-diaminonaphthalene; **DCM**, dichloromethane; **DHB**, 2,5-dihydroxybenzoic acid; **Di-FCCA**, difluorocinnamic acid; **FA**, fatty acids; **F20TPP**, *meso*-tetrakis(pentafluorophenyl)porphyrin; **GL**, glycerolipids; **GP**, glycerophospholipids; **H₂O**, water; **HX**, hexane; **MeOH**, methanol; **MTBE**, methyl tert-butyl ether; **NS**, not specified; **sDHB**, super-DHB; **SA**, sinapinic acid; **SP**, sphingolipids; **ST**, sterol lipids; **THAP**, 2',4',6'-trihydroxyacetophenone; **THF**, tetrahydrofuran.

Table 2S. Identified Lipids in Honey With 50% Laser Intensity Using a Sample:Matrix:Agent Ratio of 1:1:0.25. MALDI Matrix is DHAP and Ionizing Agent is AgTFA in THF (10 mg mL⁻¹).

Input Mass	Matched Mass	Delta	Name
404.187	404.1963	0.0093	SPBP 17:1;O2
406.187	406.1869	0.0001	NAE 16:0
406.187	406.1869	0.0001	SPB 18:1;O2
409.008	409.0563	0.0483	ST 18:4;O4
411.172	411.1754	0.0034	FA 20:5;O4
413.176	413.1782	0.0022	FA 18:3;O7
427.814	427.8171	0.0031	PS O-42:4
429.816	429.8146	0.0014	PS 41:2
431.818	431.8172	0.0008	PC 38:0
431.818	431.8172	0.0008	PE 41:0
433.820	433.8277	0.0077	IPC 40:0;O2
435.821	435.8198	0.0012	PC O-40:3
437.175	437.1725	0.0025	ST 24:6;O5
448.846	448.8588	0.0128	PC 44:3
459.181	459.1863	0.0053	FA 22:3;O
461.179	461.1815	0.0025	FA 21:2;O2
461.179	461.1815	0.0025	MG 18:2
466.786	466.7730	0.013	PS 44:8
468.782	468.7887	0.0067	PS 44:6
470.789	470.8043	0.0153	PS 44:4
517.512	517.5166	0.0046	FA 33:0;O
643.695	643.6575	0.0375	FA 42:0;O
645.695	645.6908	0.0042	FA 45:0
649.697	649.6857	0.0113	WE 44:0
680.668	680.6915	0.0235	Cer 44:0;O2
682.671	682.6684	0.0026	Cer 44:2;O2
684.673	684.6653	0.0077	CE 19:0
750.634	750.6371	0.0031	PA O-39:0
752.633	752.6399	0.0069	HexCer 39:1;O2
754.635	754.6296	0.0054	Cer 44:1;O4
754.635	754.6296	0.0054	PC O-34:0
754.635	754.6296	0.0054	PE O-37:0
756.638	756.6348	0.0032	HexCer 38:1;O2
756.638	756.6348	0.0032	HexCer 38:0;O3
758.640	758.6422	0.0022	CerP 44:1;O2
758.640	758.6422	0.0022	PC O-36:0
758.640	758.6422	0.0022	PE O-39:0
760.648	760.6450	0.003	TG 44:4
812.603	812.6012	0.0018	HexCer 38:0;O3
859.569	859.5695	0.0005	PI 37:2
859.569	859.5695	0.0005	TG 51:14;O2
861.569	861.5664	0.0026	TG 53:15;O2
863.569	863.5644	0.0046	PI 36:2
865.573	865.5702	0.0028	PS 41:7
867.577	867.5858	0.0088	PS 41:6
964.508	964.5032	0.0048	PS 41:3
966.506	966.5136	0.0076	PC 42:7
968.506	968.5134	0.0074	PC 42:7
970.509	970.5201	0.0111	SHexCer 40:1;O2
972.514	972.5199	0.0059	SHexCer 40:1;O2
974.515	974.5034	0.0116	PS 42:4

976.521

976.5190

0.002

PS 42:3

Table 3S. Identified Lipids in Honey Samples and Their Associated Codes.

Code	Lipid	Code	Lipid	Code	Lipid	Code	Lipid	Code	Lipid
HL1	ACer 48:1;O2	HL76	LPA 17:2	HL151	PC 41:1	HL226	PS 41:2	HL301	ST 27:5;O3
HL2	ACer 50:1;O2	HL77	LPA 18:0	HL152	PC 41:2	HL227	PS 44:0	HL302	ST 28:0;O
HL3	ACer 56:1;O2	HL78	LPA 18:3	HL153	PC 41:6	HL228	PS 44:2	HL303	ST 28:1;O4
HL4	CAR 16:0;O	HL79	LPA 19:0	HL154	PC 42:3	HL229	PS 44:4	HL304	ST 28:1;O5
HL5	CAR 16:1;O	HL80	LPA 20:1	HL155	PC 42:4	HL230	PS O-41:1	HL305	ST 28:1;O9
HL6	CE 22:4	HL81	LPA 20:2	HL156	PC 42:5	HL231	PS O-42:0	HL306	ST 28:2;O3
HL7	CE 24:1	HL82	LPA 20:3	HL157	PC 42:6	HL232	PS O-42:1	HL307	ST 28:2;O4
HL8	CE 26:0	HL83	LPA 20:4	HL158	PC 44:1	HL233	PS O-42:2	HL308	ST 28:2;O5
HL9	CL 74:2	HL84	LPA 22:2	HL159	PC 44:3	HL234	PS O-42:3	HL309	ST 28:2;O7
HL10	Cer 44:0;O4	HL85	LPA O-16:0	HL160	PC 44:5	HL235	PS O-42:7	HL310	ST 28:3;O2
HL11	Cer 44:1;O4	HL86	LPA O-16:1	HL161	PC O-13:1	HL236	SHexCer 42:1;O2	HL311	ST 28:3;O3
HL12	Cer 46:0;O2	HL87	LPA O-18:0	HL162	PC O-34:0	HL237	SM 36:0;O2	HL312	ST 28:3;O4
HL13	CerP 26:1;O2	HL88	LPA O-18:1	HL163	PC O-39:2	HL238	SM 36:1;O2	HL313	ST 28:3;O5
HL14	CerPE 39:1;O2	HL89	LPA O-20:0	HL164	PC O-40:4	HL239	SM 40:0;O2	HL314	ST 28:5;O3
HL15	CoA 10:2;O	HL90	LPC O-10:1	HL165	PC O-42:0	HL240	SM 40:1;O2	HL315	ST 28:5;O7
HL16	CoA 26:0;O	HL91	LPC O-14:1	HL166	PC O-42:1	HL241	SM 41:1;O2	HL316	ST 28:6;O3
HL17	CoA 6:0	HL92	LPC O-18:2	HL167	PC O-42:2	HL242	SM 41:2;O2	HL317	ST 28:6;O5
HL18	DG 26:0	HL93	LPE 14:1	HL168	PC O-42:6	HL243	SM 42:0;O2	HL318	ST 28:6;O6
HL19	DG 30:0	HL94	LPE 16:1	HL169	PC O-42:7	HL244	SM 42:1;O2	HL319	ST 29:2;O4
HL20	DG 30:3	HL95	LPE 17:2	HL170	PE 12:0	HL245	ST 19:0;O2;GlcA	HL320	ST 29:3;O3
HL21	DG 32:5	HL96	LPG 14:0	HL171	PE 44:0	HL246	ST 19:0;O3;GlcA	HL321	ST 29:3;O4
HL22	DG 33:4	HL97	LPG 14:1	HL172	PE 44:1	HL247	ST 19:1;O2;GlcA	HL322	ST 29:3;O6
HL23	DG 44:0	HL98	LPG 15:0	HL173	PE 44:2	HL248	ST 19:1;O3	HL323	ST 29:4;O3
HL24	DG 44:1	HL99	LPG 15:1	HL174	PE 44:6	HL249	ST 19:2;O2;GlcA	HL324	ST 29:4;O4
HL25	DG 44:2	HL100	LPG 16:1	HL175	PE 44:8	HL250	ST 19:2;O3	HL325	ST 29:5;O5
HL26	DG O-32:2	HL101	LPG 17:0	HL176	PE O-36:4	HL251	ST 19:3;O2;GlcA	HL326	ST 29:5;O6
HL27	DGDG 36:8	HL102	LPG 17:1	HL177	PE O-37:0	HL252	ST 19:3;O3	HL327	ST 29:6;O4
HL28	FA 16:0;O3	HL103	LPG 17:2	HL178	PE O-42:2	HL253	ST 20:2;O2	HL328	ST 29:6;O8
HL29	FA 16:1;O3	HL104	LPG 18:0	HL179	PG 16:0	HL254	ST 20:3;O2	HL329	ST 29:7;O5
HL30	FA 16:2;O3	HL105	LPG 18:1	HL180	PG 20:1;O	HL255	ST 21:0;O2;GlcA	HL330	ST 30:3;O5

HL31	FA 18:3;O7	HL106	LPG 18:3	HL181	PG 41:0	HL256	ST 21:2;O3;S	HL331	ST 30:3;O7
HL32	FA 19:4;O	HL107	LPG O-16:0	HL182	PG 41:2	HL257	ST 23:0;O5	HL332	ST 30:4;O3
HL33	FA 20:5	HL108	LPS 13:0	HL183	PG 41:6	HL258	ST 23:1;O5	HL333	ST 30:4;O7
HL34	FA 20:6	HL109	LPS 15:0	HL184	PG 42:0	HL259	ST 24:0;O4	HL334	ST 30:5;O6
HL35	FA 22:4;O4	HL110	LPS 15:1	HL185	PG 42:1	HL260	ST 24:0;O4;S	HL335	ST 30:5;O7
HL36	FA 22:5;O4	HL111	LPS 16:0	HL186	PG 42:2	HL261	ST 24:1;O2;Tau	HL336	ST 30:6;O6
HL37	FA 23:3;O3	HL112	LPS 16:1	HL187	PG 42:4	HL262	ST 24:1;O3;S	HL337	ST 30:6;O7
HL38	FA 23:3;O5	HL113	LPS O-15:1;O	HL188	PG 43:6	HL263	ST 24:1;O4;S	HL338	ST 31:7;O5
HL39	FA 23:3;O6	HL114	LPS O-16:0	HL189	PG 44:5	HL264	ST 24:1;O5	HL339	TG 41:2
HL40	FA 23:4;O4	HL115	LPS O-16:1	HL190	PG 44:6	HL265	ST 24:1;O5;S	HL340	TG 43:2
HL41	FA 24:0;O	HL116	LPS O-16:1;O	HL191	PG O-34:0	HL266	ST 24:1;O6	HL341	TG 45:0
HL42	FA 24:5;O6	HL117	M(IP)2C 36:0;O4	HL192	PG O-38:3	HL267	ST 24:2;O6	HL342	TG 45:1
HL43	FA 25:1	HL118	MG 20:0	HL193	PG O-39:1	HL268	ST 24:4;O5	HL343	TG 47:2
HL44	FA 25:2	HL119	MG 20:4;O	HL194	PG O-40:1	HL269	ST 24:5;O6	HL344	TG 47:3
HL45	FA 25:5;O6	HL120	MG 22:6	HL195	PG O-40:2	HL270	ST 25:1;O5	HL345	TG 48:1
HL46	FA 25:8;O5	HL121	MG O-19:0;O	HL196	PG O-42:2	HL271	ST 25:5;O8	HL346	TG 49:3
HL47	FA 26:1	HL122	MG O-20:0;O	HL197	PG O-42:4	HL272	ST 26:0;O	HL347	TG 50:4
HL48	FA 26:2	HL123	MG O-20:1;O	HL198	PG O-42:5	HL273	ST 26:0;O5	HL348	TG 50:5
HL49	FA 26:2;O4	HL124	MG O-21:0;O	HL199	PI 34:2	HL274	ST 26:0;O6	HL349	TG 50:6
HL50	FA 26:5;O2	HL125	MG O-21:1;O	HL200	PI 34:4	HL275	ST 26:1;O5	HL350	TG 50:8
HL51	FA 26:6;O4	HL126	MG O-23:6;O	HL201	PI 36:1	HL276	ST 26:2;O4	HL351	TG 50:9
HL52	FA 27:2	HL127	MIPC 34:0;O2	HL202	PI 37:0	HL277	ST 26:3;O3	HL352	TG 51:12;O2
HL53	FA 27:4	HL128	MIPC 34:0;O3	HL203	PI 37:1	HL278	ST 26:4;O3	HL353	TG 51:6
HL54	FA 28:6	HL129	MIPC 34:0;O4	HL204	PI 38:3	HL279	ST 26:5;O8	HL354	TG 52:7
HL55	FA 28:7	HL130	MIPC 36:0;O2	HL205	PI 38:7	HL280	ST 27:0	HL355	TG 52:9
HL56	FA 30:1;O2	HL131	MIPC 36:0;O3	HL206	PI 38:9	HL281	ST 27:0;O5	HL356	TG 53:10
HL57	FA 32:0;O	HL132	MIPC 38:0;O4	HL207	PI 39:6	HL282	ST 27:0;O8	HL357	TG 53:14;O2
HL58	FA 33:1;O	HL133	MIPC 40:0;O2	HL208	PI 39:8	HL283	ST 27:0;O9	HL358	TG 53:18;O3
HL59	FA 36:0	HL134	MIPC 40:0;O3	HL209	PI 42:1	HL284	ST 27:1;O	HL359	TG 53:8
HL60	FA 45:0	HL135	MIPC 42:0;O4	HL210	PI 42:7	HL285	ST 27:1;O2	HL360	TG 55:11
HL61	FAHFA 32:1;O	HL136	MIPC 44:0;O2	HL211	PI 43:4	HL286	ST 27:1;O3	HL361	TG 63:10
HL62	FAHFA 33:3;O	HL137	MIPC 46:0;O3	HL212	PI 43:6	HL287	ST 27:1;O4;S	HL362	TG 63:8
HL63	FAHFA 35:3;O	HL138	NAE 22:0	HL213	PI 44:12	HL288	ST 27:1;O6	HL363	TG 65:4

HL64	FAHFA 37:3;O	HL139	NAT 19:0	HL214	PI O-36:2	HL289	ST 27:1;O;S	HL364	TG 66:11
HL65	FAHFA 50:2;O	HL140	PA 20:0	HL215	PI O-37:2	HL290	ST 27:2;O	HL365	WE 22:1;O4
HL66	FAHFA 52:2;O	HL141	PA 20:1;O	HL216	PI O-37:3	HL291	ST 27:2;O3	HL366	WE 24:1;O4
HL67	Hex2Cer 34:0;O2	HL142	PA 24:3;O2	HL217	PI O-38:0	HL292	ST 27:2;O4	HL367	WE 24:2;O4
HL68	Hex2Cer 34:1;O2	HL143	PA 40:0	HL218	PI O-38:1	HL293	ST 27:2;O5	HL368	WE 25:1
HL69	Hex2Cer 36:0;O2	HL144	PA 42:1	HL219	PI O-40:6	HL294	ST 27:2;O8	HL369	WE 25:3
HL70	HexCer 39:1;O2	HL145	PA 43:1	HL220	PIP 34:1	HL295	ST 27:2;O9	HL370	WE 26:1
HL71	HexCer 40:0;O4	HL146	PA 44:1	HL221	PIP 37:4	HL296	ST 27:3;O4	HL371	WE 26:2
HL72	HexCer 43:1;O4	HL147	PA O-40:2	HL222	PS 40:0	HL297	ST 27:3;O5	HL372	WE 34:3
HL73	IPC 40:0;O2	HL148	PA O-40:4	HL223	PS 40:1	HL298	ST 27:4;O4	HL373	WE 36:0
HL74	IPC 40:1;O2	HL149	PC 14:0	HL224	PS 41:0	HL299	ST 27:4;O5	HL374	WE 38:7
HL75	IPC 44:0;O3	HL150	PC 41:0	HL225	PS 41:1	HL300	ST 27:4;O6	HL375	WE 44:0

HL, honey lipid. For details about lipid abbreviations, please refer to LIPID MAPS® database.

Table 4S. Identified Lipids in Bee Pollen Samples and Their Associated Codes.

Code	Lipid	Code	Lipid	Code	Lipid	Code	Lipid	Code	Lipid
PL1	CAR 16:0;O	PL69	LPA 20:2	PL137	PC 42:3	PL205	PI O-37:1	PL273	ST 28:1;O5
PL2	CAR 18:0;O	PL70	LPA 20:3	PL138	PC 42:4	PL206	PI O-37:2	PL274	ST 28:1;O9
PL3	CE 22:4	PL71	LPA 22:1	PL139	PC 42:5	PL207	PI O-38:0	PL275	ST 28:2;O3
PL4	CE 22:5	PL72	LPA 22:2	PL140	PC 44:3	PL208	PI O-38:1	PL276	ST 28:2;O4
PL5	CE 24:1	PL73	LPA 22:6	PL141	PC 44:5	PL209	PI O-40:6	PL277	ST 28:2;O7
PL6	CE 26:0	PL74	LPA O-18:0	PL142	PC O-12:1	PL210	PIP 34:1	PL278	ST 28:2;O;S
PL7	CL 72:2	PL75	LPA O-20:0	PL143	PC O-13:1	PL211	PIP 37:4	PL279	ST 28:3;O2
PL8	CL 74:4	PL76	LPA O-20:1	PL144	PC O-33:3	PL212	PS 40:0	PL280	ST 28:3;O3
PL9	Cer 44:0;O4	PL77	LPC 15:1	PL145	PC O-34:0	PL213	PS 40:1	PL281	ST 28:3;O4
PL10	Cer 44:1;O4	PL78	LPC O-14:0	PL146	PC O-39:0	PL214	PS 41:0	PL282	ST 28:3;O5
PL11	Cer 46:0;O2	PL79	LPC O-14:1	PL147	PC O-42:0	PL215	PS 41:1	PL283	ST 28:4;O3
PL12	CerP 26:1;O2	PL80	LPC O-18:2	PL148	PC O-42:1	PL216	PS 44:0	PL284	ST 28:5;O3
PL13	CerPE 36:0;O3	PL81	LPC O-19:0	PL149	PC O-42:2	PL217	PS 44:2	PL285	ST 28:5;O7
PL14	CerPE 37:2;O2	PL82	LPC O-20:1	PL150	PC O-42:4	PL218	PS 44:4	PL286	ST 28:6;O3
PL15	CerPE 39:2;O3	PL83	LPE 15:1	PL151	PC O-42:6	PL219	PS O-41:1	PL287	ST 28:6;O6
PL16	CoA 22:0	PL84	LPE 16:1	PL152	PC O-42:7	PL220	PS O-42:0	PL288	ST 28:6;O7
PL17	CoA 22:2	PL85	LPE 18:1	PL153	PE 12:0	PL221	PS O-42:1	PL289	ST 29:3;O3
PL18	CoA 26:0	PL86	LPE 18:2	PL154	PE 35:4	PL222	PS O-42:2	PL290	ST 29:3;O4
PL19	CoA 26:1	PL87	LPE 18:3	PL155	PE 44:0	PL223	PS O-42:7	PL291	ST 29:3;O5
PL20	CoA 2:0	PL88	LPG 15:0	PL156	PE 44:1	PL224	SM 34:2;O2	PL292	ST 29:3;O6
PL21	DG 30:0	PL89	LPG 15:1	PL157	PE 44:2	PL225	SM 40:0;O2	PL293	ST 29:3;O7
PL22	DG 30:3	PL90	LPG 16:1	PL158	PE 44:6	PL226	SM 41:1;O2	PL294	ST 29:4;O4
PL23	DG 31:2	PL91	LPG 17:0	PL159	PE 44:7	PL227	SM 42:0;O2	PL295	ST 29:5;O5
PL24	DG 32:5	PL92	LPG 17:1	PL160	PE 44:8	PL228	ST 18:4;O3;S	PL296	ST 29:5;O6
PL25	DG 33:4	PL93	LPG 17:2	PL161	PE O-36:3	PL229	ST 19:0;O2;GlcA	PL297	ST 29:7;O5
PL26	DG 42:4	PL94	LPG 18:0	PL162	PE O-37:0	PL230	ST 19:0;O3;GlcA	PL298	ST 30:2;O4
PL27	DG 44:0	PL95	LPG 18:1	PL163	PE O-42:0	PL231	ST 19:1;O2;GlcA	PL299	ST 30:3;O3
PL28	DG 44:2	PL96	LPG 18:3	PL164	PG 16:0	PL232	ST 19:2;O2;GlcA	PL300	ST 30:3;O5
PL29	FA 16:0;O3	PL97	LPG O-18:0	PL165	PG 20:1;O	PL233	ST 19:2;O3	PL301	ST 30:4;O3
PL30	FA 16:1;O3	PL98	LPG O-18:1	PL166	PG 20:1;O2	PL234	ST 19:3;O3	PL302	ST 30:4;O7

PL31	FA 16:2;O3	PL99	LPI 17:1	PL167	PG 33:0	PL235	ST 19:4;O3	PL303	ST 30:5;O6
PL32	FA 19:7;O	PL100	LPI 17:2	PL168	PG 35:1	PL236	ST 20:2;O2	PL304	ST 30:5;O7
PL33	FA 20:5	PL101	LPS 15:0	PL169	PG 35:2	PL237	ST 23:0;O5	PL305	ST 30:6;O6
PL34	FA 23:3;O3	PL102	LPS 15:1	PL170	PG 38:0	PL238	ST 24:0;O4;S	PL306	ST 30:6;O7
PL35	FA 23:3;O5	PL103	LPS 16:1	PL171	PG 41:0	PL239	ST 24:1;O6	PL307	ST 31:7;O5
PL36	FA 23:3;O6	PL104	LPS 17:1	PL172	PG 41:2	PL240	ST 24:5;O6	PL308	TG 41:1
PL37	FA 23:4;O4	PL105	LPS O-15:1;O	PL173	PG 42:0	PL241	ST 25:1;O5	PL309	TG 41:2
PL38	FA 24:0;O	PL106	LPS O-16:0	PL174	PG 42:1	PL242	ST 26:0;O	PL310	TG 42:4
PL39	FA 24:5;O6	PL107	LPS O-16:1	PL175	PG 42:3	PL243	ST 26:0;O6	PL311	TG 43:0
PL40	FA 25:5;O6	PL108	MG O-19:0;O	PL176	PG 43:0	PL244	ST 26:2;O4	PL312	TG 43:1
PL41	FA 26:2;O4	PL109	MG O-21:1;O	PL177	PG 43:6	PL245	ST 26:5;O8	PL313	TG 43:2
PL42	FA 26:5;O2	PL110	MG O-23:6;O	PL178	PG 44:4	PL246	ST 27:0	PL314	TG 45:0
PL43	FA 26:6;O4	PL111	MIPC 34:0;O2	PL179	PG 44:5	PL247	ST 27:0;O	PL315	TG 45:1
PL44	FA 28:2;O	PL112	MIPC 34:0;O4	PL180	PG 44:6	PL248	ST 27:0;O5	PL316	TG 47:2
PL45	FA 28:6	PL113	NAT 22:1	PL181	PG O-33:0	PL249	ST 27:0;O6	PL317	TG 48:1
PL46	FA 30:1;O2	PL114	NAT 23:1	PL182	PG O-33:1	PL250	ST 27:0;O8	PL318	TG 48:3
PL47	FA 32:0;O	PL115	PA 20:1;O	PL183	PG O-34:0	PL251	ST 27:0;O9	PL319	TG 49:6
PL48	FA 32:6;O2	PL116	PA 20:1;O2	PL184	PG O-35:3	PL252	ST 27:1	PL320	TG 50:5
PL49	FA 33:1;O	PL117	PA 23:2;O3	PL185	PG O-39:1	PL253	ST 27:1;O	PL321	TG 50:6
PL50	FA 42:0;O	PL118	PA 24:3;O2	PL186	PG O-40:1	PL254	ST 27:1;O4;S	PL322	TG 50:9
PL51	FA 43:0	PL119	PA 26:3;O3	PL187	PG O-42:0	PL255	ST 27:1;O5	PL323	TG 51:12;O2
PL52	FAHFA 32:1;O	PL120	PA 39:4	PL188	PG O-42:2	PL256	ST 27:1;O6	PL324	TG 52:10
PL53	FAHFA 33:3;O	PL121	PA 40:0	PL189	PG O-42:5	PL257	ST 27:1;O;S	PL325	TG 52:7
PL54	FAHFA 37:3;O	PL122	PA 42:1	PL190	PI 37:0	PL258	ST 27:2;O	PL326	TG 53:10
PL55	FAHFA 48:2;O	PL123	PA 43:1	PL191	PI 39:6	PL259	ST 27:2;O2	PL327	TG 53:18;O3
PL56	FAHFA 52:2;O	PL124	PA 44:0	PL192	PI 39:8	PL260	ST 27:2;O3	PL328	TG 53:2
PL57	Hex2Cer 36:0;O2	PL125	PA 44:1	PL193	PI 40:1	PL261	ST 27:2;O4;S	PL329	TG 53:8
PL58	HexCer 35:3;O3	PL126	PA O-37:0	PL194	PI 40:7	PL262	ST 27:2;O5	PL330	TG 54:6
PL59	HexCer 38:0;O2	PL127	PA O-40:2	PL195	PI 42:0	PL263	ST 27:2;O9	PL331	TG 63:10
PL60	HexCer 39:1;O2	PL128	PC 12:0	PL196	PI 42:1	PL264	ST 27:3;O4	PL332	TG 63:8
PL61	HexCer 42:0;O2	PL129	PC 14:0	PL197	PI 42:2	PL265	ST 27:3;O5	PL333	TG 64:15
PL62	HexCer 43:1;O4	PL130	PC 32:4	PL198	PI 42:5	PL266	ST 27:4;O4	PL334	TG 64:17
PL63	IPC 40:0;O2	PL131	PC 41:0	PL199	PI 42:7	PL267	ST 27:4;O5	PL335	WE 24:2;O4

PL64	IPC 42:0;O4	PL132	PC 41:1	PL200	PI 43:4	PL268	ST 27:4;O6	PL336	WE 34:3
PL65	IPC 44:0;O3	PL133	PC 41:2	PL201	PI 43:6	PL269	ST 27:5;O3	PL337	WE 38:7
PL66	LPA 16:1	PL134	PC 41:6	PL202	PI 44:10	PL270	ST 28:0;O		
PL67	LPA 18:0	PL135	PC 41:7	PL203	PI 44:12	PL271	ST 28:0;O5		
PL68	LPA 20:1	PL136	PC 42:2	PL204	PI 44:7	PL272	ST 28:1;O4		

PL, bee pollen lipid. For details about lipid abbreviations, please refer to LIPID MAPS® database.

Table 5S. Classification of Honey Samples According to Botanical Origin Using Principal Component Analysis.

From	Chestnut	Heather	Lavender	Multifloral	Rapeseed	Sainfoin	Trifolium	Total
Chestnut	2 100.00	0 0.00	0 0.00	0 0.00	0 0.00	0 0.00	0 0.00	2 100.00
Heather	0 0.00	2 100.00	0 0.00	0 0.00	0 0.00	0 0.00	0 0.00	2 100.00
Lavender	0 0.00	0 0.00	2 100.00	0 0.00	0 0.00	0 0.00	0 0.00	2 100.00
Multifloral	0 0.00	0 0.00	0 0.00	6 100.00	0 0.00	0 0.00	0 0.00	6 100.00
Rapeseed	0 0.00	0 0.00	0 0.00	0 0.00	1 100.00	0 0.00	0 0.00	1 100.00
Sainfoin	0 0.00	0 0.00	0 0.00	0 0.00	0 0.00	1 100.00	0 0.00	1 100.00
Trifolium	0 0.00	0 0.00	0 0.00	0 0.00	0 0.00	0 0.00	1 100.00	1 100.00
Total	2 13.33	2 13.33	2 13.33	6 40.00	1 6.67	1 6.67	1 6.67	15 100.00

Table 6S. Classification of Honey Samples According to Geographical Origin Using Principal Component Analysis.

From	Castilla La Mancha	Castilla y León	Spain	Total
Castilla La Mancha	3 100.00	0 0.00	0 0.00	3 100.00
Castilla y León	0 0.00	11 100.00	0 0.00	11 100.00
Spain	0 0.00	0 0.00	1 100.00	1 100.00
Total	3 20.00	11 73.33	1 6.67	15 100.00

Table 7S. Classification of Bee Pollen Samples According to Botanical Origin Using Principal Component Analysis.

From	Chestnut	Multifloral	Total
Chestnut	2 66.67	1 33.33	3 100.00
Multifloral	1 10.00	9 90.00	10 100.00
Total	3 23.08	10 76.92	13 100.00

Table 8S. Classification of Bee Pollen Samples According to Geographical Origin Using Principal Component Analysis.

From	Andalucía	Castilla y León	Galicia	Spain	Total
Andalucía	1 100.00	0 0.00	0 0.00	0 0.00	1 100.00
Castilla y León	0 0.00	1 100.00	0 0.00	0 0.00	1 100.00
Galicia	0 0.00	0 0.00	3 100.00	0 0.00	3 100.00
Spain	0 0.00	0 0.00	0 0.00	8 100.00	8 100.00
Total	1 7.69	1 7.69	3 23.08	8 61.54	13 100.00

Table 9S. Classification of Bee Pollen Samples According to Geographical Origin Within the Same Botanical Origin Using Principal Component Analysis.

From	Andalucía	Castilla y León	Galicia	Spain	Total
Andalucía	1 100.00	0 0.00	0 0.00	0 0.00	1 100.00
Castilla y León	0 0.00	1 100.00	0 0.00	0 0.00	1 100.00
Galicia	0 0.00	0 0.00	2 100.00	0 0.00	2 100.00
Spain	0 0.00	0 0.00	0 0.00	6 100.00	6 100.00
Total	1 7.69	1 7.69	2 23.08	6 61.54	10 100.00

Figure 1S. Comparative MALDI-TOF Mass Spectra of the Best MALDI Matrices Used in This Study.

Figure 2S. MALDI-TOF Mass Spectra Showing Main Lipids Detected in Honey With 50% Laser Intensity Using a Sample:Matrix:Agent Ratio of 1:1:0.25. MALDI Matrix is DHAP and Ionizing Agent is AgTFA in THF (10 mg mL^{-1}).

Figure 3S. Comparative MALDI-TOF Mass Spectra of Bee Pollen Samples Acquired at Different Laser Intensities.

Figure 4S. Metrics Used for Green and Blue Assessment of the Proposed Methods: A) AGREE for Honey, B) AGREE for Bee Pollen, C) MoGAPI Score for Honey and Bee Pollen, D) BAGI Score for Honey and Bee Pollen.

